

T-Test

Notes

Output Created		12-FEB-2024 21:43:43
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\Jonathan\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\AntTimes.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet5
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	6023
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each analysis are based on the cases with no missing or out-of-range data for any variable in the analysis.
Syntax		T-TEST GROUPS=Type(1 2) /MISSING=ANALYSIS /VARIABLES=SmlArena MedArena LrgArena /ES DISPLAY(TRUE) /CRITERIA=CI(.95).
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.05
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.04

Group Statistics

	Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SmlArena	Beacon	3003	95.5133	16.91648	.30870
	Random	3003	105.3867	16.91648	.30870
MedArena	Beacon	3003	199.4533	32.19287	.58747
	Random	3003	225.5867	32.19287	.58747
LrgArena	Beacon	3003	309.4467	38.06535	.69463
	Random	3003	360.0133	38.06535	.69463

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
SmlArena	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-22.616	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			-22.616	6004.000
MedArena	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-31.456	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			-31.456	6004.000
LrgArena	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-51.475	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			-51.475	6004.000

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means			
		Significance		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
		One-Sided p	Two-Sided p		
SmlArena	Equal variances assumed	<.001	<.001	-9.87333	.43656
	Equal variances not assumed	<.001	<.001	-9.87333	.43656
MedArena	Equal variances assumed	<.001	<.001	-26.13333	.83080
	Equal variances not assumed	<.001	<.001	-26.13333	.83080
LrgArena	Equal variances assumed	<.001	<.001	-50.56667	.98235
	Equal variances not assumed	<.001	<.001	-50.56667	.98235

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means	
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		Lower	Upper
SmlArena	Equal variances assumed	-10.72915	-9.01751
	Equal variances not assumed	-10.72915	-9.01751
MedArena	Equal variances assumed	-27.76200	-24.50466
	Equal variances not assumed	-27.76200	-24.50466
LrgArena	Equal variances assumed	-52.49243	-48.64090
	Equal variances not assumed	-52.49243	-48.64090

Independent Samples Effect Sizes

		Standardizer ^a	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
SmlArena	Cohen's d	16.91648	-.584	-.635	-.532
	Hedges' correction	16.91860	-.584	-.635	-.532
	Glass's delta	16.91648	-.584	-.636	-.531
MedArena	Cohen's d	32.19287	-.812	-.864	-.759
	Hedges' correction	32.19689	-.812	-.864	-.759
	Glass's delta	32.19287	-.812	-.866	-.757
LrgArena	Cohen's d	38.06535	-1.328	-1.384	-1.272
	Hedges' correction	38.07011	-1.328	-1.384	-1.272
	Glass's delta	38.06535	-1.328	-1.389	-1.268

- a. The denominator used in estimating the effect sizes.
 Cohen's d uses the pooled standard deviation.
 Hedges' correction uses the pooled standard deviation, plus a correction factor.
 Glass's delta uses the sample standard deviation of the control (i.e., the second) group.

Oneway

Notes

Output Created		25-FEB-2024 14:59:27
Comments		
Input	Data	C: \Users\Jonathan\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\ExpData.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	6023
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each analysis are based on cases with no missing data for any variable in the analysis.
Syntax	ONEWAY SmlArenaPerm MedArenaPerm LrgArenaPerm BY Type /ES=OVERALL /STATISTICS HOMOGENEITY /MISSING ANALYSIS /CRITERIA=CILEVEL (0.95).	

Notes

Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.05
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.38

[DataSet1] C:\Users\Jonathan\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\ExpData.sav

Tests of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
SmlArenaPerm	Based on Mean	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.000	1	6004.000	1.000
	Based on trimmed mean	.000	1	6004	1.000
MedArenaPerm	Based on Mean	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.000	1	6004.000	1.000
	Based on trimmed mean	.000	1	6004	1.000
LrgArenaPerm	Based on Mean	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median	.000	1	6004	1.000
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.000	1	6004.000	1.000
	Based on trimmed mean	.000	1	6004	1.000

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
SmlArenaPerm	Between Groups	146370.291	1	146370.291	511.485	<.001
	Within Groups	1718148.966	6004	286.167		
	Total	1864519.257	6005			
MedArenaPerm	Between Groups	1025451.093	1	1025451.093	989.454	<.001
	Within Groups	6222430.462	6004	1036.381		
	Total	7247881.555	6005			
LrgArenaPerm	Between Groups	3839317.148	1	3839317.148	2649.685	<.001
	Within Groups	8699622.894	6004	1448.971		
	Total	12538940.042	6005			

ANOVA Effect Sizes^a

		Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
SmlArenaPerm	Eta-squared	.079	.066	.092
	Epsilon-squared	.078	.066	.091
	Omega-squared Fixed-effect	.078	.066	.091
	Omega-squared Random-effect	.078	.066	.091
MedArenaPerm	Eta-squared	.141	.126	.157
	Epsilon-squared	.141	.126	.157
	Omega-squared Fixed-effect	.141	.126	.157
	Omega-squared Random-effect	.141	.126	.157
LrgArenaPerm	Eta-squared	.306	.288	.324
	Epsilon-squared	.306	.288	.324
	Omega-squared Fixed-effect	.306	.288	.324
	Omega-squared Random-effect	.306	.288	.324

a. Eta-squared and Epsilon-squared are estimated based on the fixed-effect model.